

Computational Design Optimization for Duct

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ABSTRACT

Diffuser is an essential element of fluid flow machines, the study of flow nature through diffuser is essential in understanding and improving the performance. The primary objective of this analysis is to examine the curved annular diffusers and to optimize the dimension of the diffuser so that the diffuser efficiency will be maximum. The velocity field at the exit of a bend diffuser system is mostly not uniform; fluctuation of pressure and its loss are high. The total pressure loss in the diffuser depends on the entry condition of the fluid and geometrical parameters. In this work, diffuser is analysed for a given inlet condition and the modified geometry is optimized to obtain pressure recovery and maximum efficiency. The performance of such diffuser depends on inlet conditions and geometry. Four different geometry shapes of diffuser are analysed and results are presented here. The diffuser is designed in CATIA and analysed using ANSYS - CFX. Using larger the better quality characteristics, the diffuser efficiency was obtained. Using the CFD results it is found that the third model geometry shape of the diffuser has given the best pressure recovery compared to the other models, the optimum diffuser geometry is 8° for diffuser angle, Diffuser length is 495 mm, and Spacer length is 340 mm. The above optimum condition was used to obtain the maximum efficiency for the curved diffuser configuration. Hence the third model can be considered as the optimized model.

Keywords: Diffuser, CFD, Pressure and velocity variation, diffuser, k-epsilon turbulence model.

INTRODUCTION

A diffuser is a mechanical device which recovers the pressure energy from the flowing fluid at the expense of its kinetic energy. Diffusers are of many types namely axial, radial and curved depending on the geometry and design and find very wide applications in the field of turbo-machinery and aerospace. Curved diffusers are finding huge applications in the field of aircraft applications due to space restrictions and design compatibility. Study of flow parameters within these diffusers has been of primary interest to researchers in the area of fluid mechanics right from the start of 21st century. Pioneer in this was Eustine (1910) who has investigated the nature of flow within the curved diffusers. The continuous, committed and collective efforts of researchers thereafter have helped in the understanding of the fluid mechanics within these diffusers. With ever increasing the computational capability and development of very strong Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) codes have results in increased research activities in this area in recent times. Curved annular diffusers diffusers are one of the popular types of curved diffusers. Generation of very strong pressure driven stream wise vortices due to inflexion in the curvature along the direction of flow make flow in these diffusers very complicated. Since now, many researchers have been carried out on this shape of the diffuser dealing with issues like effect of different inlet conditions, effect of angle of attack, effect of area ratio, effect of aspect ratio, effect of different inlet and outlet cross-section geometries, effect of angle of turn and many more on pressure recovery and non-uniformity of flow through it.

It is today's need to extract as much energy as possible from given input volume of petroleum; as the standards of carbon emission are very strict and it's our job to design a most common components which are deals with this problem, one of the most common used components in Gas engine particularly is diffuser, diffuser used to increase static pressure and maintain high outlet area as required. I was interested to enhance the performance of given standard curved diffuser. S- Shaped diffuser was studied by Gavin, Lee (2013) and also the shear stress turbulence model using ANSYS-CFX. The velocity contour was flattening in early divergent section in the outer surface; there will be highest velocity region. Among all, S-Shaped diffuser duct has good performance characteristics than the cross-sectional area expansion over its entire length.

Ernesto Benini (2006) studied the behaviour of a centrifugal compressor of a gas turbine for small scale power production. They established a procedure to improve diffuser performance. Performance investigation was carried out at different rotating speed at different operating points. The dimension of the diffuser used in compressor is optimized by using evolutionary algorithm together with CFD calculation.

Trevor J. Cox (2006) studied the diffuser in flow path between the high & low pressure turbine and their different effects. The dimension of the diffuser were optimized i.e. diffuser length and hence the engine weight reduction was achieved. The reduction of weight can be attained by keeping exit vanes as small as possible. Engine weight can be reduced by applying the concept of turning turbine frames.

In biological sense diffusion is the process of moment of molecules from high concentration to low concentration high pressure to low pressure it's not a flow, it's not convection, it's not pumped, not slid, it is just like a soaking. In Aerospace engineering diffusion means conversion of kinetic pressure energy in to static pressure Energy. Consider nozzle, this works as flow velocity is less at inlet and velocity is increased at outlet so work is not extracted nor inputted so inlet KE should get conserved in something this is the increase in acceleration at outlet and keeping the total energy constant.

Part turn or curved diffusers are used in wind tunnels, compressor crossover, air conditioning and ventilation ducting systems, plumes, draft tubes, etc. The objective of the present study is to investigate the flow characteristics within a circular cross sectioned curved diffuser and enhance its performance. The performance of the curved diffuser is characterizes by static pressure recovery and total pressure loss coefficient. As mentioned diffuser are used to recover static pressure especially in high speed gas turbine engine of aircraft. And performance is highly depends on geometrical shapes of the diffuser and inlet conditions. They are shaped as requirement ultimately the aim to use it is facilitates effective operation of the combustor by reducing the total pressure loss. There is lot of Research already made on the straight and curved shape performance but different geometries are not tried to enhance the performance.

Diffuser Working

Diffuser are works on exactly opposite of venturi effect which means when high velocity air is passed from smaller area to larger area then its velocity decreases and static pressure increases this processes on which diffusers are works. The figure 1 shows the velocity is increasing as we go towards outlet (larger area) from inlet (smaller area) this indicates that pressure is decreasing from inlet to outlet in Nozzle that is exactly opposite to that of diffuser means diffuser are reverse of nozzle.

Fig. 1: shows velocity distribution in Nozzle

For example this widely used in formula 1 car design to create more down force by providing diffuser at the rear end of the car, as car speed is high the air is flowing under the car is at very high speed then at the rear of the car sudden expansion duct is provided this causes decrease in velocity and produces very high static pressure at rear end the high speed region is considered as vacuum which pull the car towards road producing high down force. The effective diffuser should create less turbulence and more increase in static pressure by keeping the geometry as simple and compact as possible. Because diffuse are placed at very crucial place to receive air from compressor and provide it to combustion chamber so solidity of stages is the limit on dimensions of diffuser.

Figure.2: Schematic diagram of Curved Diffuser

Geometry Modelling and Working Performance:

P.K. Sinha and Mullick [1] observed by parametric Investigation that for the increase In area ratio from 1.15 to 2.15, static pressure recovery increases sharply and after this the pressure recovery increases slowly up to 2.8 and beyond the area ratio 2.8 the pressure recovery decreases steadily, after this they concluded that coefficient of pressure recovery C_{pr} for the computational investigation was obtained as 34% compared to the experimental investigation as 31%. The measurements were taken at Reynolds number 2.45×10^5 based on inlet diameter and mass average inlet velocity. Predicted results of coefficient of mass averaged static pressure recovery and coefficient of mass averaged total pressure loss are in good agreement with the experimental results.

Computational Fluid Dynamics: Domain options and boundary conditions have been given to the grid using Fluent pre-processor.

Domain options:

- Reference pressure: 0 Pa
- Solver: energy equation, continuity equation
- Initial pressure: 101325 Pa
- Simulation type: Steady state

Modeling of the Geometry and Flow Domain

1. Establish the boundary conditions
2. Generate the grid
3. Establish the simulation strategy
4. Establish the input parameters and files
5. Perform the simulation
6. Monitor the simulation for completion
7. Post-process the simulation to get the results
8. Make the comparisons of the results
9. Repeat the process to examine sensitiveness
10. Document.

Design of Curved Diffuser

Diffuser specification:

Length of the diffuser = 495 mm

Diffuser angle = 9°

Spacer Length = 440 mm

Diameter of bend tube = 90 mm

Cross section of the diffuser = Circular

Fig 3: Given curved diffuser fluid body

In the early parts of 1980's researchers started working on how to improve the performance by introducing vortex generator. The same vortex generator is modeled and analyzed with different shapes and the convergent-divergent nozzle concept is used to finalize the shape of the vortex generator. Flow through a nozzle is the basic flow concept which I had used.

If we increase the diameter from inlet to a certain distance (80-85% of total length) gradually by lengthwise and then again decrease up to outlet, we will observe that pressure will increase as we know that pressure increases when velocity decreases and as sudden expansion is taking place the pressure increases but not drastically so no turbulence creating problem also it will be considered as less attractive shape because we can't increase the diameter after a certain integer. So we need to change some geometry of the diffuser, 1st modified design in Fig. 4 will look like below this is my first cut design of curved diffuser.

Fig. 4: Modified design of diffusers fluid body

The modified geometry in Fig. 5 is better than the first one in performance, as you can see the inlet part is so designed as to increase the velocity first at immediate instance. This sudden increase in velocity then expanded gradually which causes maximum performance or maximum increase in static pressure. But the sudden increase in velocity creates a turbulence problem so that we need to optimize some of the geometrical entities.

The vortex generator will help to reduce the turbulence. What I have done, I increased the diameter at the upper side of the vortex generator so flow over it goes smoothly and steadily. And this will help to increase some static pressure,

Fig.5: Cross section of 1st modified Design of diffuser

Cone angle is kept constant otherwise if we increase the cones smaller area then it Cause's the turbulence, it is actually leakage of our pressure energy so, cone should be of less projected area but it is kept constant in all designs.

Problem Definition

The simulation is performed in ANSYS 16.0 and is based on the use of governing equation of Mass. Momentum, energy and turbulence. K-ε turbulence model is used for this assessment due to wide applications in internal flows. To construct a suitable geometry for the diffuser this helps in increase in static pressure at the outlet. To compare different cases of diffuser with different shapes and concluded on the best shape of the diffuser with highest pressure recovery.

Specification of working Models

Geometric dimension of diffuser is shown below. Unit of dimension is in millimeter. Steps used for the generation of 3-

D model are as follows:-

Create 3-D geometry using model option in toolbar. There are different types of tool available for the creation of geometry such as sketching, extrude, revolve etc.

There are different designs which have been considered for the analysis.

The test diffuser was designed with increase in area from inlet to exit and it distributed normal to the centerline as suggested by Prasanta Sinha and Anantdas [6]. Centerline was turned at 30° from inlet to exit with inlet diameter of 78 mm and exit diameter of 92.

Fig. 6: Basic working model

CFD METHODOLOGY

In all of these approaches the same basic procedure is followed.

During preprocessing: The geometry (physical bounds) of the problem is defined.

The volume occupied by the fluid is divided into discrete cells (the mesh). the mesh may be uniform or non-uniform.

The physical modelling is defined – for example, the equations of motions + enthalpy + radiation + species conservation.

Boundary conditions are defined. This involves specifying the fluid behavior and properties at the boundaries of the problem. For transient problems, the initial conditions are also defined. The simulation is started and the equations are solved iteratively as a steady-state or transient. Finally a postprocessor is used for the analysis and visualization of the resulting solution.

Below figure shows how the total CFD works.

Figure7: Working of CFD [16].

Pre-Processor

Pre-processing consists of the input of a flow problem to a CFD program by means of an operator-friendly interface. The user activities at the pre-processor stage involves geometry clean up, FE modelling like Grid and Cell generation, Selection of the physical and chemical phenomenon that need to be modeled, definition of the fluid properties and specification of appropriate boundary condition at cells.

SOLVER: Different streams of numerical solution techniques are Finite difference method, Finite element method, spectral method and finite volume method. Following steps will be performed by all the numerical methods. Approximate of the known flow variable by means of simple function. Discretization by substitution of the approximation into the governing flow equation and subsequent mathematical manipulations. Solution of the algebraic equations. The main differences between the various streams are associated with the way in which the flow variables are approximated.

Finite Volume Method.

The finite volume method (FVM) is a common approach used in CFD codes, as it has an advantage in memory usage and solution speed, especially for large problems, high Reynolds number turbulent flows, and source term dominated flows (like combustion). The first step in the control volume is to divide the domain into a number of control volumes where the variable of interest is located at the centroids of the control volume. The next step is to integrate the differential form of the governing equations over each control volume. Interpolation profiles are then assumed in order to describe the variation of the concerned variable between cell centroids. The resulting equation is called the Discretized equation. In this manner, the Discretized equation expresses the conservation principle for the variable inside the control volume.

Finite Element Method

The finite element method (FEM) is used in structural analysis of solids, but is also applicable to fluids. However, the FEM formulation requires special care to ensure a conservative solution. The FEM formulation has been adapted for use with fluid dynamics governing equations. Although FEM must be carefully formulated to be conservative, it is much more stable than the finite volume approach. However, FEM can require more memory and has slower solution times than the FVM.

Finite Difference Method

Finite difference methods describe the unknown flow variable of the flow problem by means of point samples at the node points of a grid of co-ordinates lines. Truncated Taylor series expansions are often used to generate finite difference approximations of derivation in terms of point samples at each grid point and its immediate neighbors.

Spectral Methods

Spectral methods approximate the unknown by means of truncated Fourier series of Chebyshev polynomials. Unlike the finite difference or finite element approach the approximations are not local but valid throughout the entire computational domain.

Post-Processor

As in pre-processing a huge amount of development work has recently taken place in the post-processing field. Owing to the increased popularity of engineering workstations many of which have outstanding graphics capabilities, the leading CFD packages are now equipped with versatile data visualization tools. These include:

1. Domain geometry and grid display.
2. Vector plots
3. Line and shaded contour plots
4. 2D and 3D surface plots
5. Particle tracking
6. View manipulation, Colour post script etc.

Methodology and CFD Simulation

This chapter focuses on the methodology adopted to achieve the objectives set in chapter one. The main objective is to get the values of pressure and velocity at the inlet and outlet of the diffuser. To achieve this requirement CFD analysis has been done for flow in an annular curved diffuser at Reynolds number 2.45×10^5 . The numerical results extracted from CFD simulations are compared and presented. A grid-independence study is performed to confirm the results are independent of the grid size. Time independent calculations for the flow have been performed in three dimensions for turbulent flow and k-ε turbulence model has been used.

Diffuser Efficiency: The Diffuser efficiency or effectiveness is given by $\eta = \text{Static pressure rise in actual process} / \text{Static pressure rise in isentropic process}$

$$\eta = C_{pa} / C_{ps}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Case: 1

Case: 2

Case: 3

Case: 4
Fig.8 Velocity and Pressure variations

Fig 9: static pressure distribution from Inlet to outlet

CONCLUSION

The diffuser with a bend in the preceding section was analyzed and the geometry was optimized to maximize the diffuser efficiency, the analysis and velocity & pressure variation were studied. The optimized parameter level affecting the diffuser geometry is found using CFD. The Diffuser angle is the factor which considerably affects the increase in efficiency. Spacer length has no impact on the objective much when compared to diffuser angle and length of diffuser. When there was change in shape of the diffuser in such a way that the area near the outlet was made smaller there was decrease in the value of static gauge pressure as due to contraction of the area of the diffuser there was increase in the value of velocity which led to the decrease in the static pressure. The optimum diffuser geometry is 8° for diffuser angle, Diffuser length is 490 mm, and Spacer length is 440 mm. The velocity in the first case was decreasing gradually from inlet to outlet due to expansion in the model. In second case the model area average gauge pressure at the inlet is 20 Pa and at the outlet the area average gauge pressure is 680 Pa and hence there is a pressure rise of 660 Pa. In third model the area average gauge pressure at the inlet is 16 Pa and at the outlet the area average gauge pressure is 935 Pa. In the fourth model with narrow area near the outlet the pressure at the inlet is 200 Pa and at the outlet the pressure is 47 Pa and hence there is a decrease in the value of the pressure and hence is not a good model for diffuser. In this case there was an increase in the value of velocity and hence decrease in the pressure and hence this model is not preferred for diffusers. The above optimum condition was used to obtain the maximum efficiency is 83.4% for the curved diffuser configuration.

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